

Ways of word formation. Structural peculiarities of lexicon, Types of root and affixal morphemes

Mirzaaliyeva Maftuna Ulfat qizi

4th year students at Djizzak branch of National University
of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulug'bek

Supervisor: **Zilola Abdurakhmanova**

Assistant teacher in the department of Foreign languages at Djizzak
branch of National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulug'bek

Annotation

This article is about information ways of word formation. Structural peculiarities of lexicon, Types of root and affixal morphemes.

Key words: structure, formation, morpheme, suffixes,

The word is the fundamental unit of language, it has form and content. Linguists define the word as the smallest free form found in language. Words have an internal structure consisting of smaller units. The most important component of word structure is the morpheme (Greek morphe “form” +-eme “the smallest distinctive unit”) – the smallest unit of language that carries information about meaning or function. For instance, the word builder consists of two morphemes (build – with the meaning of “construct”) and -er (indicates that the entire word functions as a noun with the meaning “one who builds”); the word houses is made up of two morphemes (the morpheme house – with the meaning of “dwelling” and the morpheme –s – with the meaning “more than one”). Some words consist of a single morpheme (e.g. the word train cannot be divided into smaller parts. Such words are called simple words and words which contain two or more morphemes are complex words. For example, one: and, boy, hunt, act; two: boy-s, hunt-er, act-ive; three: hunt-er-s, act-iv-ate; more than three: re-act-iv-ate. A morpheme is a meaning and a stretch of sound joined together. Morphemes are always used as parts of words. Thus, morpheme is a minimum sign of a given meaning with a given form (sound and graphic). One should distinguish between suffixes and inflexions in English. Suffixes can form a new part of speech, e.g. beauty – beautiful. Inflexions are morphemes used to change grammar forms of the word, e.g. work – works worked – working. Word-formation Word formation or word-building is a branch of science of the language which studies the patterns on which language forms new lexical items (expressions, words). It is a process of forming words by combining a root and affixal morphemes. There are the following ways of word-formation in English: affixation, conversion, compounding, clipping, back-formation, blending, sound imitation, sound-interchange, stress-

interchange. Depending on the morphemes used in the word there are four structural types of words in English: 1) simple (root) words consist of one root morpheme (warm, law, tables, tenth); 2) derived words consist of one root morpheme, one or several affixes and an inflexion (lawful, unmanageable); 3) compound words consist of two or more root morphemes and an inflexion (boyfriend, outlaw); 4) compound-derived words consist of two or more root morphemes, one or more affixes and an inflexion (left-handed, warm-hearted, blue-eyed).

REFERENCES:

1. Abduraxmanova, Z., & Mamurova, M. (2021). THEORETICAL APPROACH TO SPEECH DISFLUENCIES IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION. In МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ (pp. 43-45).

2. Абдурахманова, З. (2022). Analysis of pauses and interruptions as elements of linguistic production in simultaneous interpretation. Современные инновационные исследования актуальные проблемы и развитие тенденции: решения и перспективы, 1(1), 533-535.

3. Grossberg, L., Nelson, C., & Treichler, P. A. (Eds.). (1992). Music and Cultural Theory. University of Illinois Press. p 1-20, 89-105.

4. Ma'ripov J. ANTROPOSENTRIZM–TILSHUNOSLIKNING ZAMONAVIY YONALISHI SIFATIDA//Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 28. –С. 62-68.

5. Ma'ripov J. K. A BRIEF INFORMATION ABOUT TENSES //O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY VA O‘RTA. – С. 464